

Natural Probiotics Help Treat IBS

Those struggling with Irritable Bowel Syndrome should include more natural sources of probiotics such as yogurt, kefir, into their daily diet, reports a new review study out of University College Cork.

This review paper looked at 42 clinical studies that investigated the effects of probiotics therapy on IBS. They discovered that 34 of the 42

studies found a clinical benefit of consuming probiotics.

The study author's note that probiotics bacteria help reduce inflammation in the large intestine, a primary contributor to IBS symptoms. In addition, they note that probiotics may also reduce the frequency of debilitating IBS "flare-ups."

Here are all natural programs to eliminate [IBS from your life...](#)

On the other hand, learn about simple home remedy to [eliminate acid reflux permanently...](#)